

SARS-CoV-2: OF SPANISH DESCENT

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Abstract: SARS-CoV-2 is a genetically engineered SARS-COV vector which has been embedded into the backbone of bacteriophage HP2 of Nontypeable Haemophilus Influenza (NTHi). The design of SARS-CoV-2's spike (S) protein is notable for its ability to facilitate cellular entry via not only the ACE2 receptors but also ICAM-1 which becomes upregulated in a NTHI infection. Technologies used in the development of SARS-CoV-2 were patented by the Spanish National Research Council in 2006 and include methods for creating a SARS-COV vector for gene editing, particularly "gene silencing", and vaccine administration via "virus particles". This patent calls for the engineering of a SARS-COV vector using a helper virus such as HP2 for replication and/or transcription. According to this patent, the said system could be constructed using a genome of SARS-COV containing sequences encoding a heterologous reporter gene or a gene derived from a different infectious agent and the construction of a full-length cDNA, which in the case of SARS-CoV-2 was most likely performed using hnRNP Q CRISPR Activation Plasmid (h) cDNA. Further, NTHI lysates increase exosome release in the human middle ear epithelial cells. Exosomes can regulate gene expression via their miRNAs. SARS-CoV-2 shares a 76% homology with SARS-COV which is an engineering requirement mentioned in the said patent. The patent also sets forth modification principles and sequences for engineering the ORF of gene 7a. This engineering can be observed as a structural analysis has revealed that SARS-CoV-2 ORF 7a has structural homology with ICAM-1. ORF 7a plays a vital role in virus tropism allowing SARS-CoV-2 to be "guided" to gene editing targets via the hosts inflammatory secretions. Manipulation of ORF 7a to evade the hosts natural defenses against virus tropism as well as the use of NTHI lysates can cause an excessive inflammatory response or a "cytokine storm" in high-risk populations who become infected with COVID-19. This mode of engineering would necessarily classify SARS-CoV-2 a biological weapon.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, HP2, viral vectors, CRISPR, cDNA, hnRNP Q, gene silencing, CCR5

1. Introduction

The scientific community and the world at large have been misled about the origins of SARS-CoV-2, its design, and its primary mechanisms of action. This pandemic has killed roughly 4 million people worldwide and has compromised the health, safety, and livelihood of all of humanity. Confronting the truths of this matter is both urgent and essential.

It has been encouraging to see calls by the U.S. government to investigate the origins of SARS-CoV-2, however, I am afraid that the current focus of these efforts is off target. While the world has turned its focus completely to the Wuhan Lab and the “Bat Lady” in China, the more culpable country(s) and persons have gone largely unnoticed.

The U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH) and the National Institutes of Allergies and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) has provided Luis Enjuanes, a virologist at the National Center for Biotechnology, in Madrid, Spain, and his colleagues millions of dollars in funding over the past three decades. Much of Enjuanes work that was funded by the NIH / NIAID involved research on bacteriophages, influenza, coronaviruses, gain-of-function research, HIV, vaccine development, and methods for gene therapy using coronavirus vectors (1). Enjuanes, a longtime colleague of Peter Daszak of EcoHealth Alliance, was also one of the 27 scientists who signed a statement affirming the natural origin theory of SARS-CoV-2 which was published in the Lancet on February 18, 2020 (2).

In 2006, Enjuanes’ research on coronavirus derived expression systems led to a patent for the use of SARS-CoV as a gene editing tool (3). This patent details methods for using an attenuated SARS-CoV vector, more specifically a defective interfering (DI) genome of SARS-COV as a mode for gene editing and vaccine delivery. This expression system requires a helper virus as well as a full-length cDNA clone assembled in a bacterial artificial chromosome (BAC) plasmid (4). In 2015, Enjuanes’ and colleagues in Spain and Rochester, NY., wrote a protocol entitled; “Engineering Infectious cDNAs of Coronavirus as Bacterial Artificial Chromosomes”, which was partially funded by the U.S. National Institutes of Health (5).

The said patent which was issued by the WIPO to the Spanish National Research Council, details the sequence modification requirements of SARS-CoV coat proteins and S proteins. Viral tropism is the affinity of a virus for a particular cell type, tissue, or species. It has been well established that coronaviruses can be modified via manipulation of the spike (S) protein which enables engineering of the tropism of the vector (6). The expression system detailed in the said patent requires that the coat proteins of the modified virus have a sequence homology of at least 60%, preferably at least 75%, and most preferably at least 95% to the wild type of SARS-CoV proteins. Notably, the S proteins of SARS-CoV-2 share roughly a 76% and 97% of amino acid sequences with SARS-COV and RaTG13 respectively (7).

The said patent also contains sequencing data for a variety of ORF genes including ORF 3a and b, ORF 6, ORF 7a and b, ORF 8a and b, and ORF 9b. ORF 7a is significant as it has a structural homology with ICAM-1 allowing both ORF 7a and ICAM-1 to bind to LFA-1. ORF 7a

is also a critical factor in viral tropism as it plays a role in immune system modulation and the inflammatory response. Further, recent research shows the ORF 7a amino acid sequence of SARS-COV and SARS-CoV-2 are 85% similar (8). The said patent requires that the protein of gene 7a has a sequence with a homology of at least 70%, preferably at least 85%, or at least 95% to SARS-COV.

2. Background

For the past year and half, I have researched the pathophysiology of COVID-19. To date, I have published two papers (this one is the third) and one book detailing my research findings. This paper is the culmination of those findings and points to the origins of SARS-CoV-2 and helps to shed more light into the pathophysiology of a COVID-19 infection.

My first research paper entitled; *“COVID-19, The Plague that Strikes Behind the Ear”*, explored how the bacteria Nontypeable Haemophilus Influenza, a quite common gram-negative coccobacillus that colonizes the nasopharyngeal region in up to 80% of all humans, might be involved in the pathophysiology of a COVID-19 infection. I also described how a NTHI and SARS-CoV-2 coinfection would cause upregulation of ICAM-1, a binding receptor which viruses like HIV use for cellular entry via CCR5 and CXCR4 co-receptors. During ICAM-1 upregulation, the adaptive immune system responds via the release of inflammatory secretions which can lead to excessive inflammation or what is better known as a “cytokine storm”, a phenomenon seen in many COVID-19 patients with progressed disease (9).

Later, in my book; *“Informed Consent: Exposing the Eugenics Cult and Their Latest Experiment on Mankind: COVID-19”*, the NTHI – SARS-CoV-2 connection was further explored, revealing how a coronavirus might be manipulated to perform a gene editing experiment, *in vivo* (10). It has been discovered that genes encoding high molecular weight adhesion proteins of NTHI are part of important gene clusters, specifically Hmw1 and Hmw2 genes which encode B ORFs and C ORFs of NTHI (11). As a result, many scientists have developed ways to perform gene silencing procedures using this opportunistic bacterium including a group of scientists at Harvard University who identified how NTHI might be exploited and used to cause a “loss-of-function” to the CCR5 co-receptor via “virus like particles”. The work of these scientists led to the issuance of a patent on August 18, 2020, entitled; “Editing of CCR5 receptor gene to protect against HIV infection”. It should be noted that this patent was issued to Harvard University and the research was partially funded by the U.S. NIH (12).

As an Islamic Medicine Practitioner, I also examined the spiritual aspects of disease which contribute greatly to the rise of emerging infectious disease (EID). Also discussed in this work was a 2008 publication in *Nature* about the global trends in EIDs. This research, performed by Peter Daszak and his colleagues, included an analysis of a database of 335 EID events which occurred between 1940-2004. The researchers noted a correlation between the rise in EID events and the HIV pandemic. They further noted that EIDs place a huge burden on global economics and public health and that methods should be employed to control EIDs to prevent

global economic collapse and widespread disease (13). It should be noted that CCR5 has found to be upregulated in COVID-19 patients. Further, a loss-of-function to the CCR5 co-receptor is thought to eliminate certain infectious diseases like HIV, Influenza, and other viral diseases (14).

On June 3, 2021, I wrote an Open Letter to the U.S. Intelligence and Scientific Communities entitled; *“COVID-19 is a Covert CCR5 Gene Silencing Experiment using a Genetically Engineered Virus Containing Decoy Parts “*. This letter was sent to several U.S. government departments and officials including the Senate Select Committee on Intelligence, the Office of the Intelligence Community Inspector General, House Representatives Ihan Omar and Abigail Spanberger and Senators Mitch McConnell and Rand Paul. In this letter, I summarized my previous research and encouraged an investigation into the origins of SARS-CoV-2 using said research. I specifically called for an investigation into gain-of-function research involving bacteriophages of NTHi and coronaviruses done within the U.S. and abroad; Peter Daszak / EcoHealth Alliance and his research partners / associates, Bill Gates, the Wuhan Institute of Virology, and the National Institutes of Health concerning research on NTHi, CCR5 Silencing, CRISPR-Cas9 technologies, HIV/AIDS research, P6, Influenza, and HIV vaccine development, genetic drug therapies, etc., all experiments involved in the creation of Harvard University’s patent number # 10745677. Further, I expressed urgency in the performance of this investigation as COVID-19 is a biological warfare event committed against all of humanity and is a blatant violation of informed consent (15).

In this paper I will briefly address my most recent research findings on SARS-Cov-2 which points to its genetically engineered design using the Spanish patent and other research performed by Luis Enjuanes and his colleagues around the world.

3. Embedding SARS-CoV-2 into the Backbone of Bacteriophage HP2: A Pathway to Gene Manipulation

As previously mentioned, the Spanish patent details methods for using defective interfering (DI) genomes of coronaviruses might act as a vector for gene therapy with the use of a helper virus for replication and or translation. In my book; *“Informed Consent: Exposing the Eugenics Cult and Their Latest Experiment on Mankind: COVID-19”* (10), I detailed how SARS-CoV-2 was a genetically engineered coronavirus using bacteriophage HP2 of Hemophilus influenza, designed to carry out a covert gene editing procedure, specifically, a CCR5 loss-of-function experiment. It has been long established that genomes of phage P2 and of P2-related phages can serve as helper viruses especially once they become prophages (16). A study of bacteriophage HP2 of Haemophilus influenza has demonstrated the ability of prophages to inhibit gene expression (17). I have already detailed in my book how mRNA vaccines are able to disguise prophage inducing chemicals as seemingly harmless ingredients (i.e., salts, chloride, lipids). Recent research has discovered that SARS-CoV-2’s general mode of action is as a co-receptor dependent phagocyte, a type of cell capable of encompassing and digesting bacteria (18).

4. COVID-19 is a Covert Gene Editing Experiment

a. The Experiment Pt. 1: Gene Targeting via Pro-Inflammatory Cytokines

As previously mentioned, viral tropism deals with a virus's propensity for a specific cell type, tissue, or species. Viral tropism can be dictated via pro-inflammatory cytokines (19). In my paper; "COVID-19: The Plague that Strikes Behind the Ear", I described how viral infections in patients colonized with high concentrations of NTHI may be at risk as specific viruses like SARS-CoV-2, on top of a bacterial infection may significantly enhance the risk for excessive inflammation. Much like Human herpesvirus 8 (HHV-8), HIV, and AIDS, NTHI can inhibit the hosts epithelial defense proteins. Once compromised, airway epithelial cells respond to the invasion of NTHI by secreting pro-inflammatory acute phase reactants such as IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α (20-22). NTHI then increases the expression of ICAM-1 by airway epithelial cells which increases the susceptibility of viruses binding to the cells, a common method used by rhinoviruses for cellular entry (23).

In a gene editing experiment, viral tropism is essential as a coronavirus vector can be engineered to a particular genetic sequence/(s) guided by specific pro-inflammatory reactants. In the Spanish patent, the use of immunostimulant cytokines such as TNF- α , INF-g, IL-2, IL-12, or IL-18 is recommended to overcome the host's barriers designed to restrict viral tropism (3). It should be noted that such a manipulated virus will ultimately yield a highly dangerous bioweapon.

In a 2015 study, NTHI lysates were used to identify bacterial proteins and their biological effects. It was found that the most common and highly concentrated proteins found in NTHI lysates either contributed to biofilm formation (HMW 2A and HMW 1A), elude the innate immune system (IgA), or activate epithelial pro-inflammatory pathways such as Toll Like Receptor (TLR-2) signaling and NF-kB transcription factor which are mediated by outer membrane proteins (OMP5, OMP1, OMP26, OMP6 and OMP2) (24). It is important to note that OMP6 has long been studied as a potential vaccine antigen (25).

b. The Experiment Pt. 2: Gene Silencing via NTHI Exosome Release in Middle Ear

Exosomes are small vesicles that are involved in genetic signaling between cells. These vesicles contain proteins and nucleic acids such as mRNAs, microRNAs (miRNAs) or noncoding RNAs which can regulate gene function (26). In a 2018 experiment, scientists used NTHI lysate treatments on human middle ear epithelial cell (HMEEC) lines to analyze protein secretions. It was found that several heterogenous nuclear ribonucleoproteins (hnRNPs) including hnRNP A2B1 and hnRNP Q were regulated by the NTHI lysates. These hnRNPs are both involved in miRNA packing in exosomes. It is important to note that miRNAs are involved in RNA silencing and post-transcriptional regulation of gene expression (27). According to the

Spanish patent (3), a coronavirus as a vector for gene therapy would require 1) a coronavirus genome, 2) the presence of a helper virus (bacteriophage HP2 of NTHI), 3) virus assembly in a BAC, and 4) the construction of a full-length cDNA clone which could be performed using hnRPQ CRISPR Activation Plasmid (h) cDNA encoding the human SYNCRIP gene (28-29). Data has shown that expression levels of hnRNP Q influence HIV-1 replication (30).

c. The Experiment Pt. 3: Delivery of Lysates: CCR5 Loss-of-Function via Harvard Patent #10745677

This matter has been previously discussed in my book; *“Informed Consent: Exposing the Eugenics Cult and Their Latest Experiment on Mankind: COVID-19”* (10), for brevity I will summarize the main points.

Scientists at Harvard University developed methods and chemical compositions which can cause a “loss-of-function” to the CCR5 co-receptor in humans. One of these systems suggest the use of the CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing tool to cause a loss-of-function to CCR5 via mutation. According to the researchers, this may be accomplished by introducing the CRISPR-Cas9 system via mRNA virus particles. Further, to promote effective gene targeting, they also suggest combining LtxA, the GAM protein of the bacteriophage Mu, which is the endotoxin of NTHI along with a mRNA fusion. This combination would effectively become a NTHI lysate, promoting exosome release thereby initiating the gene editing procedure once a host becomes infected with SARS-CoV-2. It is important to note that translation can be delayed through modifying a sequence in the mRNA of the coronavirus vector. Essentially, the mRNA can carry a message to “delay” translation until certain conditions are met such as the administration of mRNA vaccines.

In this scenario, LtxA would increase the infectivity of CD4 T-cells which would grant the coronavirus vector, SARS-CoV-2 more access to CCR5 co-receptors for editing. LtxA is also secreted as part of the immune response which would act to facilitate effective Homology Directed Repair (HDR) through its ability to bind to the double strand breaks thereby protecting against the degradation of the DNA in the places where the edits are made (12).

d. The Experiment Pt. 4: mRNA Vaccines

Current mRNA vaccines facilitate the delivery of sodium, sugars, phosphates, and chloride which might be necessary components to activate Cas9. Vaccines also deliver mRNA which causes the process of translation. The PFIZER-BIONTECH Covid-19 vaccine includes “dibasic sodium phosphate dihydrate” which is the radioactive form of sodium phosphate (31). In a 1952 research paper entitled; “Independent functions of viral protein and nucleic acid in growth of bacteriophage”, scientists observed that radioactive phosphorus entered the bacterium increasing the replication rate of the virus giving it more control over the protein making functions of the cells (32).

Additionally, the cell wall of Gram-negative bacteria such as NTHI consists mainly of Lipopolysaccharides (LPS), an endotoxin which is released when the cell wall of dead bacteria is broken down. LPS consists of polysaccharides and lipid A. Lipid A is responsible for the toxic properties that make any invasive Gram-negative infection a potentially serious medical emergency. To circumvent this, some COVID-19 vaccines, might have been intentionally designed to act as a mechanism to deliver lipids to the bacterium to prevent NTHI from completely dying so that it can continue to function normally and produce genetic material.

This would allow SARS-CoV-2 genetic material to replicate within NTHIs' genome giving it the ability to 1) control gene expression by stimulating the lytic cycle; 2) control transcription; and 3) control the translation process. The lipid content of certain COVID-19 vaccines might also serve as part of the density-gradient centrifugation allowing rapid sediment of mRNA as NTHI has an asymmetric arrangement of phospholipids.

These topics have previously been covered in detail in my book; *"Informed Consent: Exposing the Eugenics Cult and Their Latest Experiment on Mankind: COVID-19"* (10).

It is important to note that currently, Luis Enjuanes and his colleagues at the National Centre for Biotechnology are developing the world's first intranasal vaccine for COVID-19 set to be released in 2022 (33). The creation an intranasal vaccine is logical as NTHI colonizes the ear, nose, and throat areas of almost 80% of the world's population which would allow for a very direct mode of delivery. It is also important to note that also in 2006, Spanish National Research Council was issued another patent entitled; "Vaccine Against Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Causing Coronavirus (SARS-COV). Luis Enjuanes was listed as one of the inventors (34).

5. Concluding Remarks

The COVID-19 pandemic is biological terrorism event against all of humanity. It is a gene editing experiment whereby majority of the participants (humans) are involuntary test subjects due to the intentional release of SARS-CoV-2. SARS-CoV-2 is a genetically engineered SARS-CoV vector which has been embedded in the backbone of HP2 using methods from Spanish patent no.: WO 2006/136448 and Harvard University patent no.: 10745677. The purpose of COVID-19 is to perform a covert CCR5 gene silencing experiment, *in vivo*.

Further, COVID-19 is a mass genocide attempt targeting persons of African descent, Hispanics, Native Americans, Asians, and Middle Eastern persons. It is also a population control effort targeting the world's poorest residents including those in Africa, India, and South America. The risk and side effects of this experiment include mild-to-severe reactions to SARS-CoV-2 virus particles which may result in long term disease, permanent disability, and death. It can also cause irreversible changes to your DNA and ultimately the DNA of unborn offspring. Further,

off-target editing might result in unintended chromosomal changes and ultimately birth defects in the next generation.

To date roughly 4 million people have died from COVID-19. It is time for the perpetrators to be identified and held accountable for their evil actions towards humanity. Individuals within world governments, academic institutions, the medical and scientific communities, business world, who have planned, facilitated, and/or helped in the cover-up of the origin of SARS-CoV-2 and the purpose for COVID-19 should be publicly identified and held accountable for their crimes which includes blatant violations of informed consent.

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